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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL TEA POWDER

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ABSTRACT

Herbal tea is essentially a concoction of many medicinal plant parts that are highly medicinally valuable. Herbal tea, which is a blend of herbs, is considered to have optimum therapeutic effects and is safe to drink. The aim of this study is to formulate an herbal tea with known health benefits using *Moringa oleifera*, *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger) and *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Tulsi). The phytochemicals present were also evaluated. Tea powder containing the above medicinal plants is evaluated for qualitative and quantitative estimations for carbohydrate, proteins, tannins, glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids and phenolic acid. The plants selected here are reported for various activities such as anti-inflammatory, immunostimulant, anti-bacterial, anti-oxidant, preservative etc. The phytochemical contents of the tea indicated that the herbal teas contained tannins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, proteins and glycosides. Further study is necessary to make combinations of specific herbs for treatment of different types of diseases and other health uses.

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INTRODUCTION

Tea is a common and important component of social and cultural gatherings. Tea is experiencing a renaissance in popularity as more people become aware of its health benefits. The leaves or other components of the evergreen tea plant are infusions used to make tea [1].

Herbal teas made from plants are becoming more and more popular among customers as a new trend. Many find its flavor to be cooling, slightly bitter, and astringent. This preparation helps reduce stress, weariness, anxiety, and many other symptoms while boosting immunity, maintaining activity, and rejuvenating cells [2].

Herbal tea powder, also known as tisane powder or herbal infusion powder, is a practical and adaptable way to drink herbal tea [3]. Caffeine is present in every tea that is collected from the tea plant. It is an inherent component of the plant. Because they don't truly include tea, herbal "teas" don't contain caffeine [4].

Fig:1 Herbal tea powder

Moringa oleifera:

In recent years, there has been an increase in the usage of *Moringa oleifera* leaves as a powerful ingredient in herbal tea formulations. The only genus in the Moringaceae family, *Moringa oleifera*, is a commonly grown plant in India. The plant's leaves are abundant in flavonoids, polyphenols, alkaloids, glucosinolates, isothiocyanates, vitamins, and minerals. They also have strong immune stimulating, anti-oxidant, and anti-diabetic effects [5]. Rich in anti-oxidant components, *Moringa oleifera* is a great source of macro and micronutrients [6].

Zingiber officinale:

Zingiber officinale's stem is known as ginger. The herb is widely utilized in culinary and beverage preparations as well as medical. It is a crucial component of numerous foods and beverages. One well-known natural spice is ginger. It has a spicy flavor because of gingerols, an active ingredient, are present. It has a long list of well-researched and recognized health advantages, some of which include the reduction of stress, platelet aggregation, and digestive issues like nausea, indigestion, and cramping [7].

Ocimum tenuiflorum:

Due to its many therapeutic benefits, tulsi has been used in Ayurveda for thousands of years. Tulsi is regarded as an adaptogen, helping the body adjust to stress and harmonizing many bodily functions [8]. Tulsi has a high phenol content, strong antioxidant action, and a variety of medicinal uses. In addition to being aromatic and having a delicious flavour, tulsi improves one's sense of freshness and relaxation after consumption [9].

Uses of herbal tea

- Achieving a more calm and relaxed state of mind
- supporting heart health
- aiding with stomach and digestive problems
- providing cleansing properties for the body
- promoting energy and wellness
- nourishing the nervous system
- strengthening the immune system
- providing antioxidants to the body
- boosting energy levels
- relieving stress
- stimulating the internal organs [10].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and processing of plant materials

Fresh moringa and tulsi leaves were collected from a local farm in Muneerabad, Telangana. The plant was authenticated at Botanical Survey of India which is situated in Koti, Hyderabad, Telangana. They were washed and dried at room temperature for 3-4 days. Along with moringa and tulsi leaves, peel of ginger was taken. These plant materials were then powdered by using mortar and pestle. They were then passed through sieve 60 individually to obtain uniform size of the powder.

Formulation of Herbal Tea:

The herbal tea was formulated by mixing the individual powders of moringa, zingiber officinale and ocimum tenuiflorum according to the below formula.

Table No-1: Formulation of herbal tea

Ingredients	Quantity (15 g)
<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	10 g
<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	3 g
<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	2 g

Evaluation tests:

Organoleptic Evaluation

Morphological evaluation such as color, odour and taste were carried out.

Phytochemical Screening

The formulated herbal tea powder was first extracted by heating it for 15-20mins. Then the solvent was filtered out. This was done to purify the original solvent by removing unwanted components.

1. Test for Glycosides (Keller- Killani Test):

0.5ml of glacial acetic acid was added with 4-5 drops of ferric chloride. It was then mixed with 1-2ml of extract, then concentrated sulfuric acid was added to the walls of test tube. Deep blue color indicates the presence of glycosides.

2. Test for Flavonoids (Shinoda Test):

10 drops of dilute hydrochloric acid were added in 1-2ml of extract. A piece of magnesium tungsten was then added, on shaking deep pink color indicates the presence of flavonoids.

3. Test for Tannins (Ferric chloride Test):

In 1-2ml of extract 2ml of ferric chloride was added. Dark blue color indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

4. Test for Alkaloids (Mayer's Test):

In 1-2ml of extract few drops of Mayer's reagent was added. Creamy white precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

5. Test for Saponins (Foam Test):

Drop of Sodium carbonate was added in 5ml of extract. On shaking formation of foam indicates the presence of saponins.

6. Test for Carbohydrates (Benedict's Test):

5ml of benedict's reagent was added in 2ml of extract. It was then heated for 5mins. Dark red precipitate indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

7. Test for Proteins (Xanthoproteic Test):

Few ml of nitric acid was added in 1-2ml of extract. Yellow color indicates the presence of proteins.

8. Test for Sterols (Salkowski Test):

2ml of chloroform and concentrated sulfuric acid was added in 5ml of extract. Reddish-Brown color indicates the presence of sterols.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

❖ Organoleptic Evaluation Results:

Table No-2: Organoleptic Evaluation

Color	Darkish Green
Odour	Aromatic
Taste	Astringent, Slightly Bitter

Fig:2 Formulated Herbal tea powder

❖ **Phytochemical Screening Results:**

Table No-3: Results of phytochemical tests

PHYTOCHEMICALS	RESULT	OBSERVATION
Glycosides (Keller- Killani Test)	+	Dark Blue Color
Flavonoids (Shinoda Test)	+	Deep Pink Color
Tannins (Ferric Chloride Test)	+	Dark Blue Color
Alkaloids (Mayer's Test)	-	No ppt was formed
Saponins (Foam Test)	-	No foam was formed
Carbohydrates (Benedict's Test)	+	Dark Red ppt
Protein (Xanthoproteic Test)	+	Yellow Color
Sterols (Salkowski Test)	-	Yellow color

Fig:3 Phytochemical evaluation

CONCLUSION

Herbal tea containing *M. oleifera*, *Z. officinale* and *O. tenuiflorum* was successfully formulated. The herbal tea made from combinations of ginger, tulsi, and moringa leaves is not only nutrient-rich but also has a distinct flavour with therapeutic and antioxidant qualities. Evaluation was performed by studying its morphological and phytochemical parameters. The phytochemical contents of the tea indicated that the herbal tea contains tannins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, proteins and glycosides. This combination was formulated mainly to extract its antioxidant activity but they also possess anti-inflammatory, immunostimulant, anti- bacterial, anti-diabetic, anti-cancer and many other properties. Further study and analysis are important to guarantee its therapeutic potentials and use for humans with its high nutritional value.

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